

ORGANIC FUNGICIDES. PART IV. PREPARATION OF SOME ARYLOXY FATTY ACIDS AND THEIR MERCURY DERIVATIVES

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Several aryloxy fatty acids and their mercury derivatives have been prepared preliminary to evaluation of their fungicidal activity.

Compounds of mercury, both inorganic and organic, have found considerable use as fungicides seed treatments and as mildew-proofing agents (Frear, "Chemistry of Insecticides, Fungicides and Herbicides", 1948, p. 250). While the inorganic salts are highly toxic to all other forms of life and cannot be directly applied to food plants, the organic mercurial compounds are specifically toxic for the lower organism. In this paper, organo-mercurials, derived from aryloxy fatty acids, have been prepared as it has been observed that the substituted phenoxy compounds, well known as plant-growth promoting substances, themselves become effective as herbicides and fungicides under different conditions of concentration and temperature, and this activity tends to increase with higher homologues of substituted phenoxyacetic acid (*Chem. Rev.*, 1946, 39, 199; Michaelson, Schaal and Fults, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. Proc.*, 1948, 13, 267). Their mercury derivatives are therefore expected to be more toxic to the fungi.

The aryloxy fatty acids have been obtained, as usual, by condensing substituted phenols with halogenated fatty acids in presence of caustic soda solution (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 1555). With the exception of chloroacetic acid, α -bromopropionic acid and α -bromobutyric acid have been prepared in the laboratory. The method used for the mercuration of aryloxy fatty acids is an adoption of that described by Friend ("Inorganic Chemistry", Vol. XI, part I) and Guha Sircar and Datta (*this Journal*, 1950, 27, 359). All the ten aryloxy acids have been mercurated and their mono-mercurated derivatives obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL

α -Bromo-fatty Acids.— α -Bromopropionic acid and α -bromobutyric acid were prepared by heating freshly distilled dry acids with bromine in the presence of phosphorus trichloride (Vogel, "Practical Organic Chemistry", p. 421). Their boiling points corresponded to those previously reported.

Aryloxy fatty acids were prepared by heating the appropriate phenol (1 mol.) with the halogenated fatty acid (1 mol.) and caustic soda solution (2 mols.) at 100° for 3 to 6 hours (*loc. cit.*). Some of the aryloxy acids, which were obtained as oils, solidified on cooling and were crystallised from 10% methyl alcohol or petroleum ether. Others solidified when distilled under reduced pressure. To establish their purity, their neutralisation equivalents were determined (0.1 g. of the acid, dissolved in 10 c.c. of alcohol, was titrated against 0.1 N-caustic soda solution). The following compounds have been obtained.

TABLE I

Aryloxy acid	M.p. (obs.)	B.p. (obs.)	M.p. or B.p. (lit.)	Yield.	Equivalent	
					Obs.	Calc.
<i>p</i> -Ethylphenoxyacetic acid	91°	—	90°	67.8%	179.6	180.1
<i>m</i> -Ethylphenoxyacetic acid	73°	—	—	56.8	179.4	180.1
<i>p</i> - <i>tert.</i> -Butylphenoxyacetic acid	86°	—	86.5°	88.8	210.5	208.1
<i>p</i> - <i>tert.</i> -Amylphenoxyacetic acid	50°	—	—	45.4	224.3	222.4
<i>p</i> -Ethylphenoxypropionic acid	50°	—	—	55.5	195.2	194.1
<i>m</i> -Ethylphenoxypropionic acid	51°	188°/12mm.	—	74.4	196.1	194.1
<i>p</i> - <i>tert.</i> -Butylphenoxypropionic acid	51-52°	—	165°-169/2mm.	59.3	222.8	222.4
<i>p</i> - <i>tert.</i> -Amylphenoxypropionic acid	—	210°/3mm.	—	69.7	234.0	236.0
<i>p</i> - <i>tert.</i> -Butylphenoxybutyric acid	84°	210°/20mm.	—	74.4	237.1	236.0
<i>p</i> - <i>tert.</i> -Amylphenoxybutyric acid	54°	148°/18mm.	168°/3mm.	55.5	250.2	250.2

Mercuration of Aryloxy Fatty Acids.—The aryloxy-acids were mercurated by the method of Friend (*loc. cit.*) and Guha Sircar *et al.* (*loc. cit.*): Either a mixture of equimolecular quantities of mercuric acetate in water and aryloxy fatty acid in dilute acetic acid or a mixture of yellow mercuric oxide (1 mol.) in 50% acetic acid solution and aryloxy-acid (1 mol.) in 50% alcoholic solution was heated on a water-bath till a sandy powder separated. The time required for the reaction varied from 1 to 6 hours. The precipitate was filtered and repeatedly washed with boiling water, hot dilute acetic acid and hot alcohol.

All the compounds are insoluble in water, in dilute acids and in common organic solvents. They are stable to air and light. When boiled with concentrated hydrochloric acid, they are decomposed to mercuric chloride and the corresponding aryloxy-acid.

This solution was diluted with water and mercury estimated as mercuric sulphide by passing hydrogen sulphide into it, followed by repeatedly washing the precipitate with carbon disulphide, alcohol and ether to dissolve sulphur and organic impurities (Vogel, *loc. cit.*, p. 504). The results of the analysis indicated that mono-mercurated anhydride of aryloxy fatty acids were obtained.

The following mercury derivatives have been obtained.

TABLE II

Mercury derivatives.	M.p.	% Hg.	
		Calc.	Found.
$C_6H_5.C_2H_5(-O.CH_2.COO)-Hg$ (<i>p</i>)	224° (decomp.)	52.97	51.9
$C_6H_5.C_2H_5(-O.CH_2.COO)-Hg$ (<i>m</i>)	198° (decomp.)	52.97	51.1
$(CH_3)_2.C.C_2H_5(-O.CH_2.COO)-Hg$ (<i>p</i>)	192° (liq.)	49.3	50.2
$CH_3.CH_2.C(CH_3)_2.C_2H_5(-O.CH_2.COO)-Hg$ (<i>p</i>)	160° (liq.)	47.7	48.9
$C_6H_5.C_2H_5(-O.CH.CH_3.COO)-Hg$ (<i>p</i>)	227° (liq.)	51.1	50.1
$C_6H_5.C_2H_5(-O.CH.CH_3.COO)-Hg$ (<i>m</i>)	234° (decomp.)	51.1	51.5
$(CH_3)_2.C.C_2H_5(-O.CH.CH_3.COO)-Hg$ (<i>p</i>)	248° (decomp.)	47.7	48.4
$CH_3.CH_2.C(CH_3)_2.C_2H_5(-O.CH.CH_3.COO)-Hg$ (<i>p</i>)	228° (liq.)	46.2	45.53
$(CH_3)_2.C.C_2H_5(-O.CH.C_2H_5.COO)-Hg$ (<i>p</i>)	238° (decomp.)	46.2	45.3
$CH_3.CH_2.C(CH_3)_2.C_2H_5(-O.CH.C_2H_5.COO)-Hg$ (<i>p</i>)	240° (decomp.)	44.7	45.07